

Radiochemical Separation of Silver Ions employing Cerium(IV) Molybdate Ion-exchanger

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Ceric molybdate has been synthesised under optimum conditions. The adsorption studies of silver ions were carried out by varying the amount of ceric molybdate ion-exchanger (50 to 500 mg) and the adsorption was found to remain constant at 400 mg level. The adsorption values at different pH revealed that the maximum adsorption occurred at pH 4.0. Similarly, when the contact time was varied (2–14 min), maximum adsorption was observed at a contact time of 8 min.

The adsorption of different cations on ceric molybdate under the experimental conditions mentioned above was studied with and without carrier (Table 1). As expected the percentage adsorption of the other elements was greater at 'without carrier levels' than 'with carrier'. The adsorption of the elements with carrier revealed that Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sc^{III} , Ir^{IV} , Pd^{II} , Os^{III} , Re^{VII} , Sn^{II} , Sn^{IV} , Cr^{III} , As^{III} , As^{V} , Te^{IV} , Ru^{III} , In^{III} , Cu^{II} , La^{III} , Mn^{II} , Eu^{III} and S^{VI} were adsorbed in the range 1.0–10%; Na^{I} , Se^{IV} and Fe^{II} were adsorbed to the extent of 10–50%; while Rb^{I} , Fe^{III} , Ba^{II} , Tl^{I} , Au^{III} , Cs^{I} and K^{I} were adsorbed to greater than 50%. Pt^{IV} , Sb^{III} , Sb^{V} and Cr^{VI} formed precipitate under the experimental conditions and were removed by centrifugation prior to the adsorption of silver ions. Zr^{IV} and W^{VI} interacted with the ion-exchanger. Adsorption of Au^{III} was decreased to <1.36% by washing the ion-exchanger with 50 mg of thiourea. K^{I} ions was adsorbed to 4.78% by washing the ion-exchanger with hot water. Adsorption of Zr^{IV} and Fe^{III} was decreased to <3.0% by precipitating as hydroxide and removing the precipitate prior to the adsorption of

silver ions. The separation of Ag^{I} from Cs^{I} , Se^{IV} , Ba^{II} and Rb^{I} was carried out by precipitating Ag^{I} as AgCl . The precipitate was centrifuged and dissolved in dilute NH_3 prior to adsorption. The separation of Ag^{I} from Tl^{I} was carried out by precipitating Ag^{I} as silver oxalate. Fe^{II} ions were removed by washing the resin with 40 mg EDTA.

TABLE 1—PERCENTAGE ADSORPTION OF OTHER ELEMENTS IN THE SEPARATION OF SILVER IONS ON CERIC MOLYBDATE ION-EXCHANGER

Adsorption %	Elements	
	Without carrier	With carrier
1–10	Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Os^{3+} , Re^{7+} , Pt^{4+} , Sn^{4+} , Cr^{3+} , In^{3+} , S^{6+}	Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ir^{4+} , Pd^{2+} , Os^{3+} , Re^{7+} , Sn^{2+} , Sn^{4+} , Cr^{3+} , As^{3+} , As^{5+} , Te^{4+} , Ru^{3+} , In^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , La^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Eu^{3+} , S^{6+} , Pt^{4+} , Sb^{3+} , Sb^{5+} , Cr^{6+} , Na^+ , K^+ , Cs^+ , TI^+ , Zr^{4+} , Se^{4+} , Ba^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Rb^+ , Fe^{2+} , Au^{3+}
10–50	Ir^{4+} , Pd^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , Sb^{5+} , Se^{4+} , Cr^{6+} , Cs^+ , As^{3+} , As^{5+} , Te^{4+} , Cu^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Eu^{3+} , Fe^{2+}	Na^+ , Se^{4+} , Fe^{2+}
> 50	Na^+ , Au^{3+} , K^+ , Sb^{3+} , TI^+ , Ru^{3+} , Zr^{4+} , Ba^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Rb^+ , La^{3+} , W^{6+}	Au^{3+} , K^+ , TI^+ , Ba^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Rb^+ , Cs^+ , Zr^{4+} , W^{6+}

^aWashed by appropriate reagent ^bFormed precipitate, ^cReacted with ion-exchanger

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ and other isotopes used were procured from BRIT. Gamma-emitters were counted at their corresponding photopeaks on a NaI(Tl) well-type detector in conjunction with a single-channel pulse-

Fig. 1. pH titration curve of cerium(IV) molybdate for the adsorption of Ag^+ .

height analyser. Beta-emitters were counted on an end-window type G.M. counter in conjunction with a decade scaler, timer and a high voltage unit. pH measurements were conducted with a Systronics digital pH meter.

Ceric molybdate ion-exchanger was prepared by the reported procedure¹.

The stoichiometry of the ion-exchanger was determined by dissolving ceric molybdate (100 mg) in 4 M HCl. Cerium was estimated as the oxide and molybdenum estimated gravimetrically by the oxine method^{2,3}.

The ion-exchanger capacity was determined by the pH-titration curve as explained by Topp and Papper⁴. The plot of pH vs milliequivalents of alkali added per g of ion-exchanger (Fig. 1) revealed the value to be 0.666 meq g^{-1} for Ag^+ ion.

References

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